

A Study on the Black Day of Indian History - The Jallianwala Bagh Massacre

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Introduction :

Jallianwala Bagh Massacre, Jallianwala also spelled Jallianwalla, also called Massacre of Amritsar, incident on April 13, 1919, in which British troops fired on a large crowd of unarmed Indians in an open space known as the Jallianwala Bagh in Amritsar in the Punjab region of India, killing several hundred people and wounding many hundreds more. It marked a turning point in India's modern history, in that it left a permanent scar on Indo-British relations and was the prelude to Mahatma Gandhi's full commitment to the cause of Indian nationalism and independence from Britain.

The acts were met by widespread anger and discontent among Indians, notably in the Punjab region. Gandhi in early April called for a one-day general strike throughout the country. In Amritsar the news that prominent Indian leaders had been arrested and banished from that city sparked violent protests on April 10, in which soldiers fired upon civilians, buildings were looted and burned and angry mobs killed several foreign nationals and severely beat a Christian missionary. A force of several dozen

troops commanded by Brig. Gen. Reginald Edward Harry Dyer was given the task of restoring order. Among the measures taken was a ban on public gatherings.

Rowlatt Acts :

On February 1919 Legislation passed by the Imperial Legislative Council, the legislature of British India. The acts allowed certain political cases to be tried without juries and permitted internment of suspects without trial. Their object was to replace the repressive provisions of the wartime Defence of India Act (1915) by a permanent law. They were based on the report of Justice S.A.T. Rowlatt's committee of 1918. The Rowlatt Acts were much resented by an aroused Indian public. The spirit of this legislation is aptly summed up in this popular statement of those days; "Na appeal, Na dalil, Na vakeel." Meaning "No appeal, No argument, No lawyer." To demonstrate people's resentment against the Rowlett Bill, termed Black Bills by the Indian and Mahatma Gandhi called upon the people to observe strike on 6th April. The passage of the Rowlatt Act in 1919 precipitated large scale political unrest throughout India. Ominously, in 1919, the Third Anglo-Afghan War began in the wake of Amir Habibullah's assassination and institution of Amanullah in a system strongly influenced by the political figures courted by the Kabul mission during the world war.

The Black Day :

On the afternoon of April 13, a crowd of at least 10,000 men, women, and children gathered in the Jallianwala Bagh, which was nearly completely enclosed by walls and had only one exit. It is not clear how many people there were protesters who were defying the ban on public meetings and how many had come to the city from the surrounding region to celebrate Baisakhi, a spring festival. Dyer and his soldiers arrived and sealed off the exit. Without warning, the troops opened fire on the crowd, reportedly shooting hundreds of rounds until they ran out of ammunition. It is not certain how many died in the bloodbath, but, according to one official report, an estimated 379 people were killed, and about 1,200 more were wounded. After they ceased firing, the troops immediately withdrew from the place, leaving behind the dead and wounded. The shooting was followed by the proclamation of martial law in the Punjab that included public floggings and other humiliations. Indian outrage grew as news of the shooting and subsequent British actions spread throughout the subcontinent.

The Government of India ordered an investigation of the incident, which in 1920 censured Dyer for his actions and ordered him to resign from the military. Reaction in Britain to the massacre was mixed, however. Many condemned Dyer's actions - including Sir Winston Churchill, then secretary of war, in a speech to the House of Commons in 1920 but the House of Lords praised Dyer and gave him a sword inscribed with the motto "Saviour of the Punjab." In addition, a large fund was raised by Dyer's sympathizers and presented to him.

Jallianwala Bagh became a National Movement :

Jallianwala Bagh tragedy added as fuel to the burning fire. Due to this, people's anger in all parts of the country especially in Punjab reached the peak. Jallianwala Bagh Tragedy had a profound impact on the growth of the Indian National movement in India. People started various kinds of movements to liberate India from the British state. The Massacre of Jallianwala Bagh was condemned in harsh words by various leaders of India and expressed resentment against it. Mahatma Gandhi said that this was an act of barbarism which no other example can be found and he has returned the fair Kaisar-I-Hind medal and Zulu war Medal to the Government for expressing displeasure with the British Government in return for services rendered during the great war. Ravindra Nath Tagore said about the incident, "that the time has come now the honors can explain our stigma in the absurd context of insult, as far as I am concerned, I want to stand with my country devoid of all special titles" and the same time Shri. Ravindra Nath Tagore also returned the Title of knight in protest of this Massacre Viceroy. The congress constituted a probe committee under the chairmanship of Madan Mohan Malaviya against the Jallianwala Bagh Massacre. The members of this committee were Motilal Nehru, Mahatma Gandhi, Chittaranjan Das, Abbas Tyabji, Pupul Jayakar.

Conclusion :

Being a child Shri. Udham Singh who was serving the people at Jallianwala Bagh by drinking water. That time he has been also got a bullet in his hand, but his life was saved. The incident had leaved a deep impact on him. He took oath to kill Michael dyer and avenge the crimes committed on the countrymen. On 13 March 1940, shortly after a meeting at Canton hall in London, he fired at him with his pistol and killed Michael O'Dwyer. The whole country was become happy on the

news of Dyer's murder but the law has not Merced Udham Singh who was hanged on 3 July 1940. Today he is not between us but his movement was still in the heart of the Indians.

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